

ENGLISH AS AN INTERNATIONAL LANGUAGE

Sharobiddinova Madina

Andijan state Institute of foreign languages.

English language and literature major 3rd stage, group I-20-36 student

Zuhriddinova Gulchexra

Andijan state Institute of foreign languages.

English language and literature major 3rd stage, group I-20-36 student

Madaminova Mumtozbegin

Andijan state Institute of foreign languages.

English language and literature major 3rd stage, group I-20-36 student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7993176>

Abstract: this article critically reviews and discusses English as an International Language (EIL) as an alternative to the traditional models of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) and English as a Second Language (ESL).

Key words: English as an International Language, English as a Lingua Franca, English in Colombia, Native-speakerism, Non-native speakers and teachers of English.

It is obviously known that international English is the concept of the English language as a global means of communication in numerous dialects, and the movement towards an international standard for the language. It is also referred to as worldwide English, World English, Common English, General English or Standard English.

It is an indispensable fact that significance of English as an international language. English is considered a vital medium for communication across the world. It has evolved from centuries and has found a place in every country. All the countries are working with each other via business relations, and here the most important thing is communication.

Currently, humans use language as their mother tongue. Even if, English is becoming dominant day by day. Therefore, everyone knows English very well. Such as, "How do you do", "Excuse me", "Thank you", "How much" — people that speak different languages and even do not know English are familiar with these phrases. These easy phrases are less known in French, Spanish, Russian, Arab, or Chinese although all these languages along with English are the official languages of the United Nations Organization. The reason why English became an international language shall be looked for in the historic events of the last three or four centuries, and most of all it is due to the aggressive colonial politics of the British Crown of the 17 century that English became so widespread as a result of the occupation by the island state of the most of the planet's landmass.

After they had subjugated Australia, many Asian and African countries, ancient India, and a good half of the territory of the relatively new continent namely North America, Brits arranged a large-scale sale of the resources of the colonized countries. To build trade relations they naturally used their language putting the local languages into the background.

Amidst the commercial boom of the colonialist country, other areas also showed significant progress:

- literature,
- science research,
- industrial manufacturing.

So, one of the results of the industrial revolution of 18 century was that many people became dependent on their knowing the language in which the operating manuals to innovation tools and machines were created.

The English speakers also were able to take a strong position in America — the so-called melting pot of nations — where many nations were blending in the period of mass emigration. A tough policy on the displacement of languages executed on the American mainland, contrary to the popular beliefs about the notorious American freedom and democracy, lead to the fact that, in the early 20 century, English was used as one of the tools of national unity of the US citizens.

The dominating positions of English-speaking countries were further strengthening due to the outbreak (with Britain taking part in it) of the world wars — the WWI and the WWII — and, after 1945, the world hegemony was held by the United States of America, which was happily released from British colonial dependence.

Broadly, if we observe closely, the difficulty level of a particular language varies from person to person. It also depends on the culture the individual belongs to. Such as, a person from Korea will find the Japanese language less complicated than a Britisher because of the similarities between Korean and Japanese cultures.

The language, English, should not be alien or unknown to any community. Learning English was not a big deal during British rule, as most people from different cultures became familiar with the language.

.The language, English, should not be alien or unknown to any community. Learning English was not a big deal during British rule, as most people from different cultures became familiar with the language.

Indeed, English has gone through a dual development becoming various Englishes as a result of “natural evolutionary process” and becoming an international language as demanded by the practicalities of “global communication” (Widdowson, 1997, p. 142). In fact, it is frequently unclear when the language is “a variety of the same species” or is in fact a “new one” (Widdowson, 1997, p. 140). As Burrige (2004, p. 111) puts it, “Today's weeds may become tomorrow's beautiful and rewarding species”. In order to accommodate both developments, English should be allowed to bloom into various dialects. Thus, international users of the English will not treat the language as a means of identifying themselves with the language's countries of origin, but rather as a means of engaging in international communication. The change of paradigm into EIL has allowed people of different backgrounds to use the language in a different nuance rather than in a follower mode. What needs to be done is acknowledging strengths of bilingual teachers who make up the majority of English teachers in the Expanding Circle countries, where the majority of English speakers are situated. These bilingual teachers are positive “double agents” with capabilities in the areas of pedagogy, linguistic skills, and problem solving. The capabilities put each bilingual teacher as a “model of a good language learner” (McKay, 2002, p. 45). However, similar to other aspects of EIL, this is not a simple goal to achieve. The use or non-use of English as a medium of instruction in any country is largely determined by “political and ideological grounds rather than educational ones” (Kirkpatrick, 2006, p. 71). The dominance of Inner Circle Englishes in teaching and testing areas, which is highly due to economic reasons, cannot be stopped easily.

By way of conclusion, the spread of English is no longer a simple result of migration or colonisation, rather it involves multiple reasons, backgrounds, and issues. In Indonesian context, McKay has put Indonesians as “unique in how they make use of English” (McKay, 2002, p. 37). It is appropriateness and negotiation in the use and function of English among other languages, both national and local ones, that is required. Ideally, the goal should be realisation of a “contemporary global linguistic ecology” a la Phillipson and Skutnabb-Kangas (1999, p. 20).

References:

1. Gardner, H. (1993). Multiple Intelligences: The Theory in Practice. New York, NY: BasicBooks.
2. Edwards, L. (2002). The Creative Arts: A Process Approach for Teachers and Children. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill Prentice Hall.
3. Aggleton, Peter J., and Geoff Whitty. 1985. "Rebels Without a Cause? Socialization and Subcultural Style Among the Children of the New Middle Classes." *Sociology of Education* 58:60-72.
4. Anyon, Jean. 1981. "Social Class and School Knowledge." *Curriculum Inquiry* 11:1-42
5. Педагогический подход учителя к проведению урока. INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM: a collection scientific works of the International scientific conference (25th January, 2023) – Washington, USA: "CESS", 2023. Part 26 – 355
6. The significance of innovation in teaching at the University. INDIA INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC ONLINE CONFERENCE THE THEORY OF RECENT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF PEDAGOGY

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY